

Wolf in sheep's skin? Do firms with better environmental performance really have better export performance: A study of Indian manufacturing firms

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Abstract

In this study, we try to reconcile the tension between two parallel streams of literature that posit contradictory relationships between better environmental performance and export competitiveness. We propose that developing country firms (DCFs) that perform better on direct, visible, and easily measurable indicators of environmental performance but worse on holistic measures are more likely to export. However, such firms must take substantive action (i.e., holistically improve their environmental performance), reduce their resource-use intensity, and enhance their environmental innovation performance to increase their export intensity. We substantiate our claim with data from the listed Indian manufacturing firms.

Keywords

Environmental performance, Export competitiveness, Manufacturing firms, Pollution-haven, Symbolic–Substantive action

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